

ISic0426

I.Sicily inscription 0426

Language

Latin

Type

honorific; funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni, but re-used

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 286

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]aug[---]

2. [---] Cerialis sex[vir Augustalis]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491654

EDCS 21900488

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae*

Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.7146 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 181-182 no.61 fig.65

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 383

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 679

Libertini, G. 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei italiani*. Roma. At 125

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